

Towards Inclusive Research Assessment: Recognizing Research Artefacts Beyond Publications

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Version Information

This document is an output of the ELIXIR STEERS project¹ and synergistic to its Policy Brief on Strategies for Enhancing Credit and Recognition for Research Artefacts². It is planned to be a living document that will be versioned and improved based on community input. It will be hosted on Zenodo and versioned accordingly.

- Version 1: July, 2025

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¹ ELIXIR STEERS: <https://elixir-europe.org/about-us/how-funded/eu-projects/steers>

² ELIXIR STEERS Policy Brief on Strategies for Enhancing Credit and Recognition for Research Artefacts: available on ELIXIR STEERS Zenodo Community <https://zenodo.org/communities/elixir-steers/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

Diversity of Research Activities & Artefacts

Researchers contribute to the creation and dissemination of scientific knowledge through a diverse range of **research activities** that extend beyond publishing traditional peer-reviewed articles. This includes examples such as: dataset creation and curation; research software development; standard operating procedures creation; training and educational content preparation; project management; community management; mentoring; and organizing conferences. These are activities integral to the modern research process and in most cases, such activities result in tangible outputs in the form of **research artefacts**, including datasets, software tools, training materials, or any other form of digital or physical materials. However, for some activities they may not produce tangible research artefacts (e.g., conference organization).

Lack of Credit & Recognition

Despite their essential role, these non-traditional research artefacts are often undervalued or overlooked in conventional research assessment processes (e.g., hiring, dedicated career pathways, funding decisions, etc.). In acknowledgement of this problem, initiatives like DORA³ and CoARA⁴ have started pushing towards more robust and inclusive research recognition and reward mechanisms, ensuring that diverse research-related activities and artefacts are recognised and valued. This work towards highlighting and rewarding diverse contributions encourages a holistic approach to research, incentivises researchers to strive for excellence, and fosters a culture of appreciation within the scientific community.

Document Scope & Purpose

This document is an output of the ELIXIR STEERS project and is synergistic to initiatives supporting research artefact credit and recognition reform such as ELIXIR STEERS⁵, EOSC EVERSE⁶, DORA and CoARA. It aims to support wider research activity and artefact recognition reform by providing:

1. [A. Research Activities & Artefacts Table](#)
2. [B. Controlled Vocabulary for Research Activities & Artefacts](#)

This document aims to support the transition toward broader credit and recognition for researchers beyond traditional publications by providing a comprehensive overview of research activities and artefact. It aims to define key research artefact terms and categories, outline their scope, and offer practical examples for crediting them. Additionally, it examines current recognition practices, identifies existing barriers and presents actionable recommendations to enhance attribution and integration into research assessment frameworks.

³ DORA: <https://sfdora.org/>

⁴ CoARA: <https://coara.eu/>

⁵ ELIXIR STEERS: <https://elixir-europe.org/about-us/how-funded/eu-projects/steers>

⁶ EOSC EVERSE: <https://everse.software/>

A. Research Activities & Artefacts Table

[Table 1](#) represents a mapping of research activities and artefacts in tabular format. It contains a structured collection of non-publication based research activities and their related research artefacts outputs. These are grounded in the life sciences and contain many ELIXIR⁷ specific examples but can be extended and adapted for wider use by other scientific domains.

The table defines key categories, outlines their scope with examples, and highlights both the tangible outputs (such as datasets, research software, training materials) and the essential research activities that may or may not result in concrete artefacts. The document also describes current recognition practices, barriers and suggestions for improved attribution and integration of both artefacts and activities into research evaluation frameworks.

Note on research artefacts vs activities

The table is primarily designed to capture tangible research artefacts. However, in version 1 it currently also includes less tangible artefacts and this format may be changed in version 2. The table is non-exhaustive for research activities and it must be noted that for each research artefact more than one activity could be listed towards creating it.

Note on financial remuneration

While financial remuneration is essential in return for any professional work, we only stress the credit and recognition gap aspects and therefore do not include financial remuneration as a recognition mechanism in the table. The proposed credit and recognition mechanisms can support building institutional career pathways and researcher assessment which may have an implicit impact on eventual employment roles and related financial remuneration in recognition of their work.

Note on researchers vs dedicated roles

This table is designed to highlight often under-recognised research activities and related artefacts in academia. Many of these activities are undertaken by researchers in traditional academic pathways but note these activities may be undertaken also in dedicated institutional roles such as:

- Community managers
- Communication specialists
- Project managers
- Lab managers
- Administrators
- IT specialists
- +...

Credit mechanisms and related career frameworks for such work in academia is crucial to ensure staff in academia feel recognised and valued both within and beyond the traditional academic research track.

⁷ ELIXIR Europe: <https://elixir-europe.org>

Next steps

1. Further landscaping

Table 1. is non-exhaustive and will require further landscaping and community input to ensure it correctly aligns to the diverse nature of research activities and artefacts.

2. Controlled vocabulary standardisation

With the version 2 of this document, once the defined controlled vocabulary is in place for research activities and artefacts, it will be used to correctly standardise and be used to overhaul the table terminology to be of universal understanding.

Table 1. Research Artefact Table

Research Artefact Table						
(V1 - July, 2025)						
Data						
Research artefact	Research activity	Definition	Examples	Current recognition barriers	Suggested recognition mechanisms	Relevant initiatives
Curated Dataset / Knowledgebase	Curating (bio)data	The extraction, annotation, and organization of biological information from literature or experimental data into structured databases or knowledgebases. This involves interpreting complex data, applying controlled vocabularies/ontologies, and ensuring data quality and consistency, making it more computable and useful.	Curating data professionally or as part of the community for a knowledgebase such as one of the ELIXIR Core Data Resources e.g. - UniProt - Cellosaurus - Human Protein Atlas	Often perceived as a technical or repetitive task supporting larger database projects. Individual contributions can be submerged within the collective effort, and the work may not lead to traditional first-author publications, though database publications may list curators.	Ensure data curation efforts are captured (e.g. with platforms such as APICURON) and represented meaningfully for the user (e.g. on their ORCID). These captured and shared curation efforts should then be taken into consideration when assessing a researcher's collection of outputs. Accreditation programmes for data resources to recognise quality and impact such as ELIXIR Core Data Resource status which can be recognised as	ELIXIR Core Data Resources ELIXIR STEERS Project International Society of Biocuration EOSC Task Force on Research Careers, Recognition and Credit FAIRsharing APICURON

					<p>part of a researcher's outputs during assessment.</p> <p>Encourage registering knowledgebases on FAIRsharing for a citable DOI and taking its citation count into consideration during researcher assessment. (Looking beyond only scholarly publication citations)</p>	
FAIR Data Package / Metadata Record	FAIRifying data/ Research data management	The process of making research data FAIR - Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable. This includes adding comprehensive metadata, using standard formats/ontologies, depositing in appropriate repositories, and ensuring clear licensing, often a	<p>Support turning local data (e.g. from lab/project) into curated data entry contributions available on public deposition databases such as the ELIXIR Deposition Databases</p> <p>e.g. -EMDB -IntAct</p>	Time-intensive and often seen as a technical or service task, rather than a direct research output. Benefits are often long-term and community-wide, making individual attribution difficult without dedicated data papers or specific acknowledgements.	Ensure research data management and FAIRification efforts are captured (e.g. with platforms such as APICURON) and represented meaningfully for the user (e.g. on their ORCID). These captured and shared curation efforts should then be taken into consideration when assessing a researcher's collection of outputs.	<p>ELIXIR Deposition Databases</p> <p>ELIXIR Research Data Management Community</p> <p>ELIXIR-UK Dash Fellowship</p>

		significant effort beyond initial data collection.	- LIPID MAPS Implementing research data management best practice for example those on: - RDMkit		Ensure this role is institutionally recognised and has a clear career development path to foster and encourage this vital work.	
Training						
Research artefact	Research activity	Definition	Examples	Current recognition barriers	Suggested recognition mechanisms	Relevant initiatives
Training Module / Protocol / Tutorial	Creating training materials	Creating, updating, and disseminating training resources like protocols, tutorials, workshop slides, etc.	Training material output examples can be found hosted on: - TeSS (Training eSupport System) e-Learning module course examples can be found on: - ELIXIR Slovenia e-Learning platform Standardised	Materials are frequently for internal use, shared informally, and rarely published or cited. The effort is substantial but often invisible to the wider academic community and traditional metrics.	Ensure training materials shared in public resources such (e.g. TeSS/GitHub/Zenodo) are visibly captured on a trainer's ORCID and taken into consideration during researcher assessment.	ELIXIR Training Platform ELIXIR-GOBLI Train-the-Trainer Programme ELIXIR Splash

			lessons created in lesson templates: - ELIXIR lesson template			
Workshop Delivery / Course Completion (as instructor)	Delivering training Organising training	The direct delivery of instructional content and practical guidance to individuals or groups. This includes leading workshops, conducting tutorials, demonstrating techniques or software usage, and facilitating learning sessions, often utilizing training materials that may have been developed separately. The focus is on the act of teaching and imparting skills/knowledge through active instruction.	Delivering a specific course at an institution e.g. -5 ECTS module course Running a dedicated workshop on a specific topic: e.g. -Workshop at a conference such as the ELIXIR All Hands Meeting - TeSS-Registered Workshops - Galaxy workshops - Bioconductor workshops	Often informal, internal, and lacks formal outputs like publications. Impact can be hard to quantify beyond immediate participant feedback, making it difficult to include in traditional academic metrics.	As above, ensure both the course and any related outputs are captured in a relevant training registry and reflected visibly on the researcher's ORCID profile. During assessment ensure this is taken into consideration.	ELIXIR Training Platform
Software						

Research artefact	Research activity	Definition	Examples	Current recognition barriers	Suggested recognition mechanisms	Relevant initiatives
Research Software / Code Repository	Contributing to research software	Developing, maintaining, and enhancing software tools and code scripts used for research. This includes writing new code, debugging, adding features, optimizing performance, and ensuring compatibility with various systems. This can range from small scripts for data analysis to complex scientific applications.	Contributing to research software hosted on for example: - GitHub - GitLab	While essential for modern research, contributions can be undervalued if not accompanied by a dedicated software publication. Often seen as a means to an end (generating results for a paper) rather than a primary research output in itself, especially for contributions to existing projects.	Ensure research software efforts are meaningfully captured and represented on a researcher's software accounts (e.g. GitHub profile) and ORCID for consideration during researcher assessment. Ensure any software is published and considered during researcher assessment: -Tools on bio.tools -Workflows on WorkflowHub -Containers on Biocontainers	EOSC EVERSE OA7: Research Software ELIXIR STEERS
FAIR Software Release / Documented Codebase	FAIRifying research software/ Research software management	Making research software and code fair - Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable. This involves version	Creating a software management plan for a software service e.g. - Software	Similar to data, this is often viewed as a support activity or "good practice" rather than novel research. The significant effort in documentation, testing, and packaging	Software repositories shared by a researcher on their CV/ORCID can be used to assess research software management efforts and this information can	EOSC EVERSE OA7: Research Software ELIXIR STEERS

		control (e.g., Git), thorough documentation, clear licensing, using standard formats/languages, providing example use cases, and ensuring portability e.g. containerization to ensure others can use and build upon the code.	management plan template Implementing research software quality best practice for example those on: -RSQkit	often goes unacknowledged in publication-centric evaluations unless the software itself is a major citable output.	then be considered during researcher assessment. Future work is ongoing in ELIXIR STEERS & EOSC EVERSE EC projects to semantically capture meaningful efforts at the software repository level for capturing specific research software quality contributions. Some early outputs of this work include: -STEERS M3.1 -EVERSE D5.1	RSQkit
Research support						
Research artefact	Research activity	Definition	Examples	Current recognition barriers	Suggested recognition mechanisms	Relevant initiatives
Community Engagement Report / Event Delivered / Strategy Document	Community management	Organizing and fostering scientific communities, such as managing mailing lists, online forums, organizing seminars or workshops (not as primary	Many diverse examples of Community management outputs exist such as: -Node websites e.g. ELIXIR UK	Contributions are often intangible, relying on "soft skills" and behind-the-scenes work. Impact is diffuse and community-wide, making it hard to measure and attribute to specific	Implement peer-nomination awards and regular acknowledgements in group meetings or newsletters. Formally recognise	The EC Communities of Practice Playbook

		<p>instructor/developer), facilitating collaborations, organising outreach activities or maintaining community resources/websites. This often supports a broader research field or project</p>	<p>-ELIXIR EOSC strategy document</p> <p>-ELIXIR Community event</p> <p>-ELIXIR newsletters</p>	<p>individuals for formal academic credit.</p>	<p>community leadership roles (e.g., Working Group Chair) in performance reviews.</p> <p>Support the creation of a portfolio of community engagement activities that can be added to an ORCID or cited in CVs for consideration during funding applications and researcher assessment.</p>	
<p>Administrative Record / Compliance Document</p>	<p>Administrative activities</p>	<p>Essential administrative tasks required for research operations, such as grant reporting (post-award management), ethics applications and renewals, safety compliance paperwork, equipment maintenance logs, managing lab orders, financial reconciliations, or navigating</p>	<p>Many diverse examples of administrative activity outputs exist such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Completing post-award financial and progress reports for a grant. -Submitting and managing ethics approval documentation for a research project. 	<p>These are essential research enabling tasks, but are generally recognized as non-research activities. They do not usually generate citable outputs and are considered operational overhead, thus lacking visibility and academic reward mechanisms.</p>	<p>While often not a tangible or publicly available research output, excellence in research administration activities can be recognised through institutional recognition awards, professional development opportunities, and career progression pathways for research support staff.</p> <p>Acknowledging this work in the narrative of</p>	

		institutional procedures. These tasks support research but are not scientific outputs themselves.	(Examples are generally not publicly available to link to)		grant applications can highlight a team's efforts.	
Peer review						
Research artefact	Research activity	Definition	Examples	Current recognition barriers	Suggested recognition mechanisms	Relevant initiatives
Published Peer Reviewed Article	Peer reviewing articles	The critical evaluation of scholarly work, such as journal manuscripts, or conference submissions by experts in the same field.	Peer reviewing articles for life science journals and publishing platforms such as for the ELIXIR F1000Research Gateway .	Article peer review process is often anonymous and the significant effort is not formally recognized as a citable output. This "invisible work" is crucial for maintaining scientific quality but is rarely accounted for in research assessment.	Encourage use of services that track, verify and showcase peer review work, such as ORCID. Promote open peer review models where the review itself is a citable and attributable output. Journals and funders can provide formal certificates or acknowledgements.	
Funded grant (Based on peer review outcomes)	Peer reviewing grants	The critical evaluation of grant submissions by experts in the same field.	Peer reviewing of grants for the EOSC OSCARS open call	Grant peer review process in most cases is completely anonymous and the significant effort is not formally recognized as a citable output. This	Funding bodies could offer formal recognition through certificates or by listing panel members in annual reports. This activity should be a	

				"invisible work" is crucial for maintaining scientific quality but is rarely accounted for in research assessment.	recognised professional service in institutional career progression frameworks and researcher evaluation.	
Patents						
Research artefact	Research activity	Definition	Examples	Current recognition barriers	Suggested recognition mechanisms	Relevant initiatives
Patent	Creating and contributing to patents	The creation of novel, inventive, and industrially applicable outputs such as methods, tools, algorithms, that are 'patented' for legal protection, granting the holder exclusive rights to the invention for a set period.	Many ELIXIR resources, such as Ensembl and UniProt , are frequently cited in patent applications, demonstrating their foundational role in innovation. -Detailed ELIXIR patent contributions	Contributions of individual researchers to large, underlying data resources or software that are later cited in patents often go unrecognized. The direct link between their work and the resulting intellectual property is not always visible or formally acknowledged.	Implement institutional policies to formally acknowledge contributors to underlying research outputs that are cited in patents. The citation of data and software in patents should be tracked as an impact metric for both the resource and its contributors.	ELIXIR Europe Impact

B. Building a Controlled Vocabulary for Research Activities & Artefacts

Vocabulary need and current status

A controlled vocabulary defining research activities and artefacts will bring value to researcher credit and recognition reform through enabling a universal understanding of what they entail. In version 1 of this document (*July, 2025*) we lay the foundation for this vocabulary by identifying trusted, widely recognised sources that can inform the development of a common and coherent framework for the recognition of research activities and artefacts.

Potential sources for building a controlled vocabulary

- [COAR Controlled Vocabulary for Repositories](#)
- [OpenAIRE Graph - Research Products](#)
 - Relevant vocabularies: [publications](#), [data](#), [software](#), & [others](#)
- [Scientific Knowledge Graphs Interoperability Framework \(SKG-IF\) - Research Products](#)
- [SCoRO, the Scholarly Contributions and Roles Ontology](#)
- [Open and Universal Science Project \(OPUS\) - Indicators and Metrics to Test in the Pilots](#)
- [Hidden Ref report - Shaping the future of research evaluation](#)
- [CERIF](#)
- [DATACITE resource types](#)

Next steps

To complete the vocabulary of research activities and artefacts, the following actions are required and will inform the version 2 update of this document:

1. Identifying existing vocabulary building blocks

This work will be further developed with the goal of extending established vocabularies and introducing new terms where needed. Ideally, the choice of inputs to build upon will be those containing:

- **Research activity:** effort by researchers
 - OPUS or HiddenREF may be suitable
- **Research contributions/artefacts:** research activity outputs
 - COAR's Controlled Vocabulary for Repositories may be suitable

Some research activities may not result in tangible outputs, and it is relevant that the final vocabulary explicitly accounts for how these contributions can be identified and recognised.

2. Determining an integrated or separate vocabulary to capture activities and artefacts

There are two possible approaches for ultimately capturing the diversity of research artefacts and activities in vocabulary format:

1. Two separate vocabularies: **individually** capturing research activities and research artefacts
2. One integrated vocabulary: **jointly** both research activities and research artefacts